

User stories ODISSEI Portal

Tom Emery, Lucas van der Meer

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This document was written in preparation for developing the ODISSEI Portal. The Portal will be developed between 2020 and 2024 by ODISSEI, the Dutch national infrastructure for the social sciences (odissei-data.nl). For questions, please contact info@odissei-data.nl.

1 Portal

By lack of a better name, in this document, Portal refers to the whole of the following three parts:

- External (meta)data suppliers (DANS EASY, CBS Microdata, SHARE, ESS...).
- An interface to find datasets; the ODISSEI dataverse instance (developed by DANS) and the Social Science semantic prototype (developed by VU). For this purpose the Portal team will improve the search function, where the challenge lies in the semantic tuning and harmonisation of the metadata of the large number of different datasets.
- Data node (a better name is data manager, data broker, or data notary), a middleware that can facilitate a data access request between the user, data owner and analysis environment (e.g. ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer, SURF Research Cloud, Data Exchange, Google Drive, the researcher's own desktop computer).

2 Background information

- One of ODISSEI's key aims is to stimulate collaboration (e.g. data sharing) between its member organisations.
- With DANS, ODISSEI is creating a user agreement involving ODISSEI data: all data and metadata that has been financed, resourced, analysed, archived, disseminated, or generated using ODISSEI infrastructure. All users will be obligated to sign this document.
- The document, still in draft form, states that all metadata (column headers, codebooks, questionnaires, accessibility, etc.) must be publicly available through the ODISSEI Portal under a Creative Commons (CC0) license. We can impose conditions.

3 General requirements

3.1 Search Functionality

- A researcher should be able to use the portal to look for where certain concepts appear in included datasets. For example, a search for 'mental health' could return results on survey questions associated with mental health (these are very common question items in surveys, even when the survey itself is not on mental health) or on the data at CBS on anti-depressant subscriptions.
- Identifying concepts across data is great but for research the real difficulty is the concurrent measurement of concepts. You therefore really want to search for a dataset that contains concept X and concept Y rather than doing an independent cross-reference. For example, I would want to know how 'mental health' relates to 'work' and so I would want to limit results to datasets that contain both.

3.2 Linkage Functionality

- Within the datasets, it would be good to describe in the metadata the key linkage variables that are shared across datasets (NB: the actual linkage will not be done in our environment; we just provide a search engine for *which linkage variables are available*). CBS has a set of standard linkage keys to link the respondents across different datasets that could be flagged in the existing datasets to help illustrate linkages. This would enhance the search functionality as you could search for such linkage variables to understand what linkage opportunities existed. At the moment, the vast majority of linkage is on the BSN number (and its anonymized forms). However, linkage could be done based on school or work ID's, or even religious affiliations. There are a wide range of data that could be linked here and the main reason it isn't used is because these linkages are not well documented or findable.
- As you could then potentially search for datasets that carry two 'concepts' but the query would be able to use the linkages to find instances where linkages could be made that enabled such an analysis. For example, if I searched for 'mental health' and 'bullying' it might be that a social survey has good data on self-reported bullying but lacks adequate measures on mental health. The results of the search would then not only return studies in which both concepts are

measured but also where both concepts could be measured through linkage (i.e. by returning a result that shows the bullying study + linked data from CBS).

- Ultimately, it would also be good to identify the exact percentage overlap in linkage as well. For example, when looking at the personal ID number of people between two independent social science studies there is very low likelihood that an individual appeared in both so the statistic would likely be 0:0. However, with most social surveys the data can be linked to CBS, in which case the statistics would read something like 100:0.01. This would indicate that 100% of the units in the social survey dataset can be linked to CBS data but that only 0.01% of the individuals within the CBS data are in the social survey dataset. This feature would also be especially helpful when examining linkages between CBS datasets.

3.3 Access Functionality

- All data in the portal should be flagged for its access requirements ([Data Tags](#) initiative could be helpful here). Once flagged, it should be possible for the portal search results to suggest a linkage or access platform for usage and the necessary links to get it done. For example, if the data that I want to link is all open access then it will just say download these datasets here and here. For example, I want to search 'Mental Health' and 'Parks'. The search could return a result that says this mental health study contains a geo-spatial variable (e.g. municipality) which can be linked to open access data from Statline on green spaces). These files can be downloaded via this link and this link.
- For more sensitive cases, there will be restrictions. For example, if the portal result identifies survey data that can be linked to CBS data then it would contain a link to the CBS microdata access service and the process of getting this set up. We hope to expand the range of data we include beyond CBS and so this will become increasingly diverse. If this can link into a standardized access platform that can handle a single request for multiple data sources this would be ideal.

4 Use case 1

4.1 Epic

Wouter de Vries (fictional), PhD student at Erasmus University Rotterdam. He is studying children of migrants in the Netherlands, for which his supervisor pointed him to the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) dataset.

In particular, he wants to know how many children immigrants from different descent get on average ($N \geq 30$) (e.g. Surinams 1,8; Maroccans 2,5).

4.2 User story

The GGP turns out to contain an insufficient number of migrants in the Netherlands. Therefore, Wouter is looking for additional data.

Wouter looks for the variable 'Number of children', specifically for migrants. Whether a dataset contains migrants can be a property of the specific dataset, may be a variable in the dataset (yes/no), or hidden in the dataset (birthplace, birthplace parents).

4.3 Desired situation

In the new Portal, Wouter should easily find the (1) dataset '[Families of Poles in the Netherlands](#)' (FPN), that is currently available in EASY, the (2) CBS dataset [perinatal registrations](#), and (3) the following datasets and specific variables that are currently available in the LISS Data Archive (LDA)¹:

- The [initial questionnaire](#): all new LISS panel members fill out when they become a panel member (longitudinal, since 2010).
- All monthly datasets with [background variables](#) from all households. These datasets contain a variable 'origin' or 'herkomstgroep' (longitudinal since 2007).
- The single wave study [Threatening Identities: Interaction and Conflict in the Multicultural Netherlands](#) (cross-sectional)
- The [European Social Survey MTMM](#) (cross-sectional)
- The LISS Core Study (longitudinal since 2007)
- Studies conducted in the Immigrant panel (which ran from 2010-2014, longitudinal).

He should also easily find out if the way to measure children per family in FPN, CBS, and LDA is the same as in the GGP.

4.4 Current situation

4.4.1 Finding FPN

The queries '[children migrants](#)' and '[kinderen migranten](#)' in EASY result in only three and one results, respectively. The search function searches metadata such as title and description, but not the variable names since these are only in the codebooks, that are in PDF format. Data owners were not stimulated to upload the codebooks in a machine-readable format.

> Migrants National Identification and the National Dimension of Cultural Consumption			
Date:	2014-03-10	Audience:	Social sciences
Creators:	Das, Prof.dr. J.W.M. (CentERdata - Institute for data collection and research - Tilburg University);...		Behavioural and educational sciences
Relevance:	100% relevant		Leisure and recreation studies
Description:	This study examines to what extent <u>migrants and children</u> consume cultural goods from the country of	Access:	Demography
		Submitted:	Other
			2014-12-12

It is unlikely that Wouter would have found FPN. If he would have, though, he could not immediately view the FPN data or codebooks since these are restricted by the data owner. The data owner was never stimulated to consider open access for at least the codebooks.

¹ More information on LDA can be found at the end of this document

4.4.2 Finding CBS data

Finding CBS datasets and variables is only possible via the CBS Microdata catalogue. The process of finding them is cumbersome. For more information, see [use case 2](#).

4.4.3 Finding LISS datasets and variables

Although all LISS studies are also archived at DANS, it is unlikely Wouter would have found the relevant LISS datasets and variables there, since EASY does not have the metadata indexed.

Via the LDA site itself, using search terms like 'children migrants' but also 'origin', 'herkomst', 'children', 'born', and 'immigrant', Wouter easily finds the studies. The LDA uses [Questasy](#) for querying, which is based on DDI 3. All metadata (studies, questions, variables and publications) from the available LISS studies are indexed and searchable.

The screenshot shows the LISS panel data archive website. The main content area includes a blue header with the 'LISS PANEL' logo and text: "LISS panel data archive. The LISS panel consists of more than 4,500 households, comprising almost 7,000 individuals that complete online questionnaires every month." Below this is a search bar with the text "Search the data archive" and a search button. To the right, a sidebar lists "Background Variables" (1 Background Variables), "Core Studies" (2 Health, 3 Religion and Ethnicity, 4 Social Integration and Leisure, 5 Family and Household, 6 Work and Schooling, 7 Personality, 8 Politics and Values, 9 Economic Situation: Assets, 10 Economic Situation: Income, 11 Economic Situation: Housing), and "Assembled Studies".

4.4.4 Comparing the GGP, FPN and LDA datasets

The [common variable classification standard DDI](#) is not used in EASY. In fact, most researchers do not know or use DDI. The larger datasets such as GGP and SHARE do use DDI. This way Wouter cannot check if 'children per family' is the same across GGP and FPN.

The LDA is based on DDI, which means Wouter can compare datasets from the GGP and the LDA.

4.4.5 Requesting access

For the FPN data, Wouter can request access to the data owner via EASY. In this case, the data owner will grant access to non-commercial parties.

For CBS, he needs to contact the CBS Microdata department. Only employees of dedicated research departments are eligible for access. Access can only be conducted for research purposes. There are costs involved. For more information, see [use case 2](#).

For LDA, accessing and downloading the data requires Wouter to sign a [data statement](#). Data are available for non-commercial scientific purposes.

4.4.6 Conducting the research

For FPN and LDA, Wouter downloads the datasets and codebooks to his own computer and conducts the research. In the LDA, if he prefers, he can create his own 'shopping basket', only selecting the variables relevant for his research.

For CBS, the research is conducted in a strictly closed environment on CBS premises, either the CBS Remote Access (RA) environment for regular computing, or the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC). The output data are only released after a manual check for personal data by two CBS employees (four-eye principle).

4.4.7 Archiving

There is no obligation (nor real stimulus) for Wouter to properly archive his results back into EASY.

CBS requires that the result will be published (in peer-reviewed journals, on the institute's website...). The CBS source data remain available for replication studies. No archiving requirements of the output data apply.

The LISS data statement requires Wouter to provide a copy of all publications based on the data from the LISS panel. Publications will be archived, indexed and made available through the LISS Data Archive.

5 Use case 2

5.1 Epic

Inge de Bruin (fictional) is an Assistant Professor at VU Amsterdam, working at the National Twin Registry (NTR) group.

Via the NTR, Inge has access to a large database of genetic information from twins in the Netherlands. For a focus group within NTR, she collected additional birth care data (N = 20). Her goal is to explore whether there is a difference in childbirth costs of mothers suffering from schizophrenia as compared to mothers without this condition. Since there are genetic markers for schizophrenia, Inge will conduct a genome-wide association study (GWAS).

5.2 User story

Inge is at a preliminary stage of her research and is searching for data regarding childbirth and healthcare costs on an individual level, to complement her genetic data. She expects that the government may have these data available to researchers, but she does not know what institution might provide such access, nor do her colleagues.

5.3 Desired situation

Inge should easily find the variable 'Zvw kosten geboortezorg' (health care costs birth care per individual), which is included in the CBS (micro)dataset [healthcare costs](#).

She should also find the CBS (micro)dataset concerning [perinatal registrations](#) (probably even more are relevant to her).

5.4 Current situation

5.4.1 EASY

Inge knows EASY. In EASY, she can find some interesting datasets by searching for '[childbirth](#)' and 'bevalling', but not administrative data since CBS Microdata metadata are not available in EASY. (Whether the datasets found in EASY are useful for Inge, is irrelevant for this use case.)

14 RESULTS IN PUBLISHED DATASETS

☰ List 🗺 Map

› Data from: Women's experiences of mistreatment during **childbirth**: a comparative view of home

Date:	2018-03-19T14:04:40.000+0100	Audience:	Life sciences, medicine and health care
Creators:	Hameed, Waqas; Avan, Bilal Iqbal	Access:	Other
Relevance:	100% relevant		
Description:	woman. However, many women seeking childbirth services, especially those in low-income countries su...		

› Family and Household (LISS Core Study)

Date:	2008-03-01	Audience:	Social sciences
Creators:	CentERdata - Institute for data collection and research - Tilburg University; Das, Prof.dr. J.W.M. (...)		Sociology
Relevance:	51% relevant		Behavioural and educational sciences
Subject:	Partnership and childbirth intentions	Access:	Other
		Submitted:	2018-04-19

5.4.2 The CBS Microdata catalogue

Finding the dataset

Even if she were to find the [CBS Microdata catalogue](#), she would only be able to [query](#) the tailor-made datasets ('maatwerk') of previous studies, and not the core microdata catalogue (CBS never built a search function for it, for unknown reasons).

Zoekresultaten Maatwerk

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The core-catalogue and the codebooks are only available for manual browsing, and only in Dutch. Finding the right data requires substantive knowledge of the [terminology](#) and the structuring of the datasets. Using the user's browser's built-in search functions is the best way of finding datasets.

With the queries 'bevalling' and 'kosten', the ['perinatale'](#) dataset is not found. Solution: semantic graph where perinatale relates in some way to bevalling/childbirth?

Finding the variables

The codebooks, containing metadata like the variables that are available, are only available in non-machine-readable [PDF format](#), that you can download if you found the dataset.

CBS will provide us with an XML export of their underlying metadatamodel in fall 2020.

Conclusion

The current best way of finding the datasets that contain the desired variables, is by having a meeting with the CBS Microdata team (or by manually going through all files). The Portal team will try to improve that.

5.4.3 Requesting access

Only employees of dedicated research departments are eligible for access. All university scientific staff members are eligible.

Access can only be conducted for research purposes. A specific research 'top-down' research question has to be provided and access is provided on a need to know basis. Bottom-up (data guides the research) is not permitted.

After an intake meeting, CBS will send a quote. The costs are only for labour (e.g. support, output check, data preparation), and not for the data themselves (since these have been collected via taxpayer money).

Both the department and the individual researcher(s) sign an agreement with CBS. The former is focussed on i.a. financial and intellectual property matters; the latter on confidentiality.

5.4.4 Conducting the research

The research is conducted in a strictly closed environment on CBS premises, either the CBS Remote Access (RA) environment for regular computing, or the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) at SURF.

The output data are only released after a manual check for personal data by two CBS employees (four-eye principle).

5.4.5 Archiving

CBS requires that the result will be published (in peer-reviewed journals, on the institute's website...).

The CBS source data remain available for replication studies. No archiving requirements of the output data apply.

6 Use case 3

Researchers working with the Nederlands Centrum Jeugdgezondheid (NCJ) would like to collate data from 47 regional associations that operate Consultatiebureaus across the country. Each organisation is inclined to provide the data but would prefer to work under an arrangement where analysis could be conducted remotely and they could maintain full control over the data. The NCJ would like to identify a trusted third party who could act as a broker and provide secure access or system for allowing controlled analysis to be conducted.

7 Use case 4

This is an advanced use case that we would envisage for the very long term. A researcher is interested in understanding the determinants of school dropouts.

About the LISS Data Archive

The LDA contains the monthly datasets with background variables (since 2007) available for download. Furthermore, longitudinal data from the [LISS Core Study](#) is available, which covers a broad set of topics. In addition to this, over 200 projects and cross-sectional studies are available for download.

The LISS Data Archive (Questasy) has a DDI 3.1 and 3.2 export function. All metadata from the archive can (in principle) be made available for an external search portal. This requires a lot of server load, so the plan is to start caching individual studies in the near future.

Abbreviations and terms

Data suppliers

GGP	Generations and Gender Programme
NTR	National Twin Registry
NCJ	Nederlands Centrum Jeugdgezondheid
FPN	Family of Poles in the Netherlands
LISS	Longitudinal Internet Studies for the Social sciences
LDA	LISS Data Archive
CBS RA	The Remote Access facility in which it is permitted to analyse anonymised, highly-detailed microdata from CBS (Statistics Netherlands)

Metadata

DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
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Other

GWAS	Genome-wide association study
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